

Emotional Intelligence in Women with Premenstrual Syndrome

Mrs. Kalaiamutha Navaratnarajah, Research Scholar (Ph.D), Department of Psychology, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, India - 608002.

Dr. Padmasundari Singaram, Assitant Professor, Department of Psychology, Government Arts College (Autonomous), Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India – 641018

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) is characterized by a wide range of physical, emotional, and behavioral symptoms that occur during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle that adversely affect daily functioning. Women in their reproductive years are affected by Premenstrual Syndrome which causes emotional symptoms such as irritability, anxiety, depression, and mood swings. The concept of emotional intelligence refers to the ability to understand, regulate, and perceive one's own and other people's emotions. Researchers have found that higher levels of EI are associated with better mental health outcomes, including better stress management, resilience, and a general sense of well-being.

Methodology: It is the purpose of this study to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and symptoms associated with Premenstrual Syndrome in women. As part of this study, 50 women between the ages of 20 and 45, who were diagnosed with PMS in accordance with DSM-5 criteria, were assessed using two instruments. The first was the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS) and the second was the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII) to understand the correlational effect.

Results: The results indicates that the majority of participants in the study suffer from moderate to severe PMS symptoms, highlighting the fact that this condition has a significant impact on the sampling population. The study also revealed that higher emotional intelligence (MEII) is associated with lower PMS symptom severity as measured by the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII). As indicated by the significant negative correlation between MEII scores and PMSS scores, all four subscales have a significant negative correlation.

Conclusion: These findings conclude that emotional intelligence contributes significantly to the mitigation of PMS symptoms. The findings of this study emphasize the key role that emotional intelligence plays in managing the symptoms of Premenstrual Syndrome. The study suggests that enhancing emotional intelligence can be an effective way of reducing PMS symptoms and assisting in developing a multifaceted approach to addressing PMS,

taking into account the psychological as well as socio-demographic aspects of the condition.

KEYWORDS: Emotional Intelligence, Premenstrual Syndrome, Correlational Study & Marital Status

1 INTRODUCTION

An individual who suffers from Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) displays a variety of physical, emotional, and behavioral symptoms during the luteal phase of their menstrual cycle, which can adversely affect their quality of life and daily functioning. There is a significant number of women of reproductive age who suffer from premenstrual syndrome (PMS). The symptoms of PMS can include a variety of physical, psychological, and behavioral symptoms and can negatively affect a woman's quality of life and daily functioning during the luteal phase of her menstrual cycle. Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) is a multifaceted condition that affects a substantial proportion of women in their reproductive years, causing emotional symptoms such as irritability, anxiety, depression, and mood swings. Physical discomfort is often exacerbated by these emotional symptoms. As a result of a wide range of physical, emotional, and behavioral symptoms, PMS occurs during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle and can significantly affect one's ability to function daily (Yonkers et al., 2008) and Emotional symptoms of PMS, including irritability, anxiety, depression, and mood swings, are particularly distressing and can aggravate physical discomforts (Lustyk et al., 2004). Several key areas of investigation are hormonal fluctuations, neurotransmitter imbalances, and genetic factors, which are considered key to understanding PMS's underlying causes. For the development of more effective treatments and providing relief to those suffering from this condition (Rapkin & Winer, 2009), understanding these mechanisms is essential. The behavioral symptoms that are associated with PMS can range from social withdrawal to decreased motivation to difficulty staying focused (Biggs & Demuth, 2011). As a result, people can feel isolated and frustrated because of these behavioral changes, which can impair their ability to perform at work and socialize with others. A variety of physical symptoms are associated with PMS, including bloating, breast tenderness, headaches, and exhaustion (Biggs & Demuth, 2011). It is possible for these symptoms to be severe enough to interfere with women's daily lives, causing them to struggle with maintaining their usual routines. Among other things, sleep patterns, appetite, and

appetite control may also change, thereby contributing to decreased levels of well-being in general (Cunningham et al., 2009).

The concept of emotional intelligence (EI) has gained prominence in recent years as an essential component of managing one's emotional and psychological well-being. Emotional Intelligence refers to the capability of understanding, regulating, and perceiving one's own and others' emotions. There has been research which indicates that higher levels of EI are associated with better mental health outcomes, including the ability to manage stress, to be resilient, and to have a general sense of well-being. It includes skills like emotional awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. In recent years, Emotional Intelligence (EI) has been identified as a critical aspect of managing the psychological impact of PMS, as it allows one to perceive, understand, manage, and regulate their emotions. Emotional Intelligence has emerged as one of the most important factors in understanding and managing psychological well-being as well. A person's emotional intelligence (EI), or their ability to perceive, understand, manage, and regulate their emotions, encompasses skills like emotional awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills (Goleman, 1995). Researchers have consistently demonstrated that individuals with higher levels of EI have better mental health outcomes, such as increased resilience, increased stress management, and improved psychological well-being (Schutte et al., 1998).

The potential role of emotional intelligence in managing PMS symptoms has received relatively little attention despite extensive research on PMS and its impact on women's lives. It is notable that there is a substantial gap in literature, given that a substantial body of evidence suggests that people with higher emotional intelligence are more capable of coping with emotional challenges and maintaining psychological resilience. Women with PMS require effective interventions that can help them manage the emotional aspects of this condition, and understanding how EI and PMS interact is crucial to developing these interventions. EI training and development could be incorporated into treatment plans for women with PMS if it is found to be associated with reduced PMS symptom severity. There is a potential benefit to this approach in that it will lead to a more holistic and effective approach to managing PMS, which in turn will improve the quality of life of many women. The literature has paid limited attention to the potential role of emotional intelligence in mitigating PMS symptoms, despite the significant impact PMS has on women's lives. The findings are surprising, since substantial evidence indicates that people with high EI are better able to deal with emotional challenges and maintain psychological resilience (Mayer et al.,

2008). For a deeper understanding of how emotional regulation skills can affect PMS symptoms and severity, it is crucial to examine the relationship between EI and PMS. In order to better understand how emotional regulation skills affect the severity and management of PMS symptoms, it is crucial to explore the relationship between EI and PMS.

The use of adaptive coping strategies by individuals with higher EI is also more prevalent in individuals facing emotional challenges, which contributes to their overall mental health and resilience (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). It has not been extensively studied whether there is a direct correlation between EI and PMS, however related research provides some insight. In a number of populations, interventions aimed at improving emotional regulation have been shown to reduce psychological distress and improve emotional regulation (Brackett & Salovey, 2006). (Petrides et al., 2004) has shown that training programs designed to improve EI reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression, which are also common among women with PMS. It seems that these findings indicate that in order to manage PMS effectively, it might be worthwhile to enhance EI and integrate EI training and development into the management strategies for PMS. Understanding the interplay between EI and PMS may pave the way for innovative interventions that aim to integrate EI training and development into the management strategies for PMS. Researchers might be able to develop holistic treatments that address both the physical and emotional aspects of PMS, thereby improving the quality of life for many women if a strong link between high EI and reduced PMS symptoms is proven. It examines how Emotional Intelligence can influence the mental health and well-being of women suffering from Premenstrual Syndrome, filling a critical gap in the literature. It offers new avenues for supporting women's mental health and well-being in the context of PMS by exploring this relationship, which can inform future research and clinical practice. It is difficult to manage PMS because it encompasses such a wide range of symptoms, and treatment options include lifestyle changes and dietary adjustments, as well as medications such as hormone therapy and antidepressants. In order to manage PMS effectively and mitigate its impact on daily life, healthcare providers, family members, and friends play a crucial role in providing support (Freeman, 2003).

Overall, this study aims to fill a critical gap in the literature by investigating the role of emotional intelligence in the treatment of women with Premenstrual Syndrome in order to fill this critical gap in the literature. The purpose of this exploration is to provide valuable insights that can inform future research and clinical practice, offering new opportunities for supporting women's mental health and well-being in the context of PMS as well as offering new avenues for supporting future research and clinical practice.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 AIM

This study aims to investigate the correlation between women's emotional intelligence and symptoms caused by premenstrual syndrome (PMS). Women with premenstrual syndrome were examined using the correlational research design in order to find out the relationship between emotional intelligence and symptoms of premenstrual syndrome.

2.2 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- To study the severity level of premenstrual symptoms in women.
- To study the emotional intelligence among women with premenstrual syndrome.
- To study the correlation between emotional intelligence and premenstrual syndrome symptoms in women.

2.3 HYPOTHESES

- There will be a significant difference in physical, emotional and behavioral symptoms in women with premenstrual syndrome.
- There will be significant differences in emotional intelligence among women with premenstrual syndrome.
- There will be a significant correlation between emotional intelligence and premenstrual syndrome symptoms in women.

2.4 SAMPLE

In this study, 50 women aged 20 to 45, diagnosed with PMS in accordance with the criteria of DSM-5, were recruited as the sample group for the study. Through the purposive sampling method, the participants were selected in Hyderabad through gynecological clinics and online support groups. Inclusion criteria included regular menstrual cycles with a confirmed diagnosis of PMS and exclusion criteria included pregnancy, breastfeeding, any psychiatric disorder other than PMS, or any use of hormone replacement therapy that could affect menstrual cycle regularity.

2.5 TOOLS

2.5.1 Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS)

The PMS questionnaire is a comprehensive assessment tool designed to assess the severity and frequency of PMS symptoms. It includes a variety of questions pertaining to

physical, emotional, and behavioural symptoms experienced during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle during the luteal phase. The questionnaire consists of 40 items and participants are asked to rate the severity of their symptoms on a scale of 1 (Never) to 5 (Always) based on the severity of their symptoms. A symptom severity rating is given with four categories: "no symptoms", "Mild", "Moderate" and "Severe".

2.5.2 Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII)

A validated instrument such as the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII), an instrument that provides a thorough assessment of emotional intelligence within four critical domains of an individual's life, can be used to measure multiple dimensions of Emotional Intelligence. This MEII test includes four areas: Interpersonal Awareness, Intrapersonal Awareness, Interpersonal Management, and Intrapersonal Management. A total of 100 items are included in the test, and each item is scored with a value between 1 (Yes) and 0 (No) that describes the quality of the subscale from very good to very poor.

2.6 PROCEDURE

Participants were informed about the study's purpose and provided written consent. They completed a demographic questionnaire that collected information on age, education, occupation, and marital status. Participants were asked to complete the PMSS and MEII during the luteal phase of their menstrual cycle. The luteal phase was identified based on the participants' self-reported menstrual cycle dates, ensuring that the assessments captured the peak period of PMS symptoms. After completion of data collection scoring of all collected data was done according to the manual of each tool.

2.7 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All demographic variables, PMSS scores, and MEII scores were calculated using descriptive statistics, as well as means and standard deviations for continuous variables while frequencies and percentages were used for categorical variables. A Pearson correlation coefficient was computed to identify the structure and direction of the relationship between PMS symptoms and Emotional Intelligence scores. This analysis assisted in identifying the strength and direction of the relationship between PMS symptoms and Emotional Intelligence.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The study sample consisted of 50 women aged 20-45 diagnosed with Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS). The demographic distribution is demonstrated in the graphs given below:

3.1.1 Figure-1: Gives demographic data based on age range

Figure-1: Gives demographic data based on age range

The figure-1 effectively illustrates that the greatest number of women diagnosed with Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) belong to the age group that falls between 20-29 years (54%), after which it drops to the 30-39 years age group (32%), and then falls to the 40-49 years age group (14%).

3.1.2 Figure-2: Gives demographic data based on Education

Figure-2: Gives demographic data based on Education

Figure-2 demonstrating the educational background distribution of a sample of fifty women diagnosed with Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) across three categories: intermediate education, graduate education, and postgraduate education. A similar analysis reveals that 20% of the sample population (n=10) has achieved an intermediate level of education, while 50% of these women (n=25) have achieved a graduate level of education and 30% of these women (n=15) have reached a postgraduate level of education.

3.1.3 Figure-3: Gives demographic data based on Occupation

Figure-3: Gives demographic data based on Occupation

This above figure shows a breakdown of the occupations that a sample of fifty women diagnosed with Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) have across four categories, namely IT Employee, Banker, Teacher, and Housewife. This indicates that 12 women, or 24% of the women population, are employed in the IT sector, 8 women, or 16% of the women with Premenstrual Syndrome, are employed as bankers, 18 women, or 36% of the sample population, work as teachers and 12 women, or 24% of the sample population, are homemakers. Among the sample population, teachers represent the majority, followed by information technology employees and homemakers, and bankers represent the smallest group. This study provides a clear and immediate overview of the occupational distribution among these women, which emphasizes the predominance of teachers.

3.1.4 Figure-4: Gives demographic data based on Marital Status

Figure-4: Gives demographic data based on Marital Status

This above figure shows the distribution of the marital status of fifty women diagnosed with Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS). Based on the sample population, can categorize the sample population into two marital status groups, such as Single and Married. Almost half of the sample population, or 23 women, are single, showing a significant percentage of women in the sample are single. In addition, 27 women, or 54 percent of the sample population, are married, thus constituting more than half of the sample population. Considering this representation, we can see that the majority of the sample population consists of married women, followed closely by those who are single.

3.1.5 Figure-5: Gives Mean and Standard deviation Scores for the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS) and Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII)

Figure-5: Gives Mean and Standard deviation Scores for PMSS and MEII

In the figure-5, the mean scores and standard deviations are presented for the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS) and the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII). The scores provided by these questionnaires give us insight into the severity of premenstrual symptoms as well as the participants' emotional intelligence.

A mean score (M) of 122.3 was reported by the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory, with a standard deviation (SD) of 14.7, which indicates that participants displayed moderate to high levels of emotional intelligence, with some variations between groups. There is also a discussion of each subscale's scores and the mean score for interpersonal awareness is 30.5, which indicates the average ability of the sample to understand and interpret other people's emotions and behaviors. This indicates a relatively high level of self-awareness and understanding of emotions and behavior among the sample. Intrapersonal awareness scores average 32.1 out of four subscales, which was the highest average score. According to the results of this study, the mean score for interpersonal management among the sample is 29.4. This is indicative of the average level of ability among the sample to manage and navigate interpersonal relationships efficiently and effectively. In the intrapersonal management subscale, the mean score is 30.3, the lowest of all the subscales, which implies that the sample has a slightly lower ability to manage its own emotions and behaviors.

This study examined the aggregated severity of premenstrual symptoms experienced by the participants by using the premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS), based on a mean score of 34.6, with a standard deviation of 8.4. The PMSS represents the cumulative severity of premenstrual symptoms experienced by the participants. It was determined that the physiological subscale of the PMSS had a mean score of 12.3 and a standard deviation of 3.2, indicating moderate levels of physical discomfort among the participants. This subscale measures symptoms such as bloating, breast tenderness, and headaches. The psychological subscale of the PMSS recorded a mean of 15.8 with a standard deviation of 4.1. This subscale measures mood swings, anxiety, and irritability, which indicate moderate to high psychological distress. There was a mean score of 6.5 on the behavioral subscale of the PMSS, whereas the standard deviation was 2.3, suggesting a moderate impact on behavior, compared to the other subscales. This subscale also assesses changes in social behavior, such as withdrawal and difficulty concentrating.

It is apparent from the graph that there is a variation in the impact of premenstrual symptoms across different domains, with psychological symptoms being the most prominent. In order to understand the participants' emotional intelligence, the MEII scores may provide a context for understanding their coping strategies for PMS, as well as their levels of emotional intelligence.

3.1.6 Figure-6: Gives the distribution of Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS) Severity Levels

Figure-6: Distribution of Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS) Severity Levels

It is shown in the graph above that the patterns of severity of Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) among the participants have been grouped based on their PMSS scores. According to the severity levels, the symptom intensity levels are categorized into mild, moderate, and severe, so that it is possible to gain a clear picture of the prevalence of the different types of symptoms within the population.

Among the participants in this study, 12 (24%) reported mild PMS symptoms, which indicates that a smaller portion experience low-level symptoms that are likely to be manageable without significant interventions. In the sample of 50 participants, 22 (44%) fell into the moderate category. This is the largest group, suggesting that most participants are experiencing symptoms that are more pronounced and may require some kind of management or intervention in order to manage or resolve them. The study also shows that 16 participants (32%) reported severe PMS symptoms, and this group experienced the highest level of severity, negatively affecting their quality of life and daily functioning. The distribution of

symptoms in the sample indicates that a substantial number of participants suffer from severe symptoms, requiring more intensive management. The graph presented above indicates that the majority of participants in the study suffer from moderate to severe PMS symptoms, highlighting the fact that this condition has a significant impact on the sampling population. As well as these findings, the study also found that the severity of PMS (physical, psychological, and behavioral aspects) varied significantly across severity levels and that women with severe PMS scored higher on all three subscales in comparison to those with mild or moderate PMS.

3.2 Correlation Analysis

3.2.1 Table-1: Gives Correlation between MEII Subscales and PMSS Scores

MEII Subscale	Correlation PMSS (r)	p-value
Interpersonal Awareness	-0.32	0.02*
Intrapersonal Awareness	-0.29	0.04*
Interpersonal Management	-0.35	0.01*
Intrapersonal Management	-0.27	0.05*

*Significance: $p < 0.05$

An analysis of the correlation between various subscales of the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII) and the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSS) is provided in the following table. This table demonstrates the strength and direction of the relationship between emotional intelligence subscales and PMS severity by presenting correlation coefficients (r) along with corresponding p-values.

The correlation coefficient of -0.32 observed between interpersonal awareness and PMSS scores suggests a moderately negative relationship between interpersonal awareness and PMSS scores. It is statistically significant that higher interpersonal awareness is associated with lower PMSS scores, which indicates that PMS symptoms are less severe or fewer.

According to the Intrapersonal Awareness correlation coefficient, intrapersonal awareness and PMSS scores are moderately negatively correlated. A p-value of 0.04 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant, indicating that higher intrapersonal awareness is associated with less PMS symptoms.

In relation to interpersonal management, the correlation coefficient of -0.35 indicates a moderate negative relationship between interpersonal management and PMSS scores with a

p-value of 0.01, which indicates that better interpersonal management skills are associated with fewer PMS symptoms.

There is a moderate negative correlation between intrapersonal management and PMSS scores because the correlation coefficient for intrapersonal management is -0.27. A p-value of 0.05 indicates statistical significance, indicating a lower level of PMS symptoms is associated with higher intrapersonal management.

3.3 CONCLUSION

In this study, higher emotional intelligence (MEII) is associated with lower PMS symptom severity as measured by the Mangal Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEII). As indicated by the significant negative correlation between MEII scores and PMSS scores, all four subscales have a significant negative correlation. It has been discovered that women who are more aware of their own as well as others' emotions tend to experience less severe symptoms of PMS. This awareness may allow them to manage their emotional responses more effectively, reducing the impact of PMS on their daily lives. The ability to manage one's own emotions and interpersonal relationships effectively has been linked to fewer and less severe PMS symptoms and women who have better skills in these areas may be able to cope with PMS more effectively, thereby alleviating its emotional and psychological burden.

These results suggest that emotional intelligence is one of the most important factors contributing to the mitigation of PMS symptoms. These findings suggest that emotional intelligence contributes significantly to the mitigation of PMS symptoms. The findings of this study emphasize the key role that emotional intelligence plays in managing the symptoms of Premenstrual Syndrome. It has been concluded that higher emotional intelligence associated with less severe PMS symptoms as a result of higher emotional intelligence. It is evident that higher emotional intelligence is associated with less severe PMS symptoms, which suggests that interventions aimed at enhancing emotional intelligence could be beneficial for women suffering from PMS. There seems to be a moderate negative correlation between emotional intelligence subscales and PMSS scores, which suggests that enhancing emotional intelligence can be an effective way of reducing PMS symptoms and assisting in developing a multifaceted approach to addressing PMS, taking into account the psychological as well as socio-demographic aspects of the condition.

In order to validate these findings and explore their practical applications, future research should focus on developing and testing EI-based interventions tailored to women suffering from PMS. It is also essential to conduct longitudinal studies in order to understand

how enhanced EI is able to help manage PMS over the long run and increase overall well-being as a result. In addition to better emotional regulation skills, women with high EI may also possess better control of their PMS symptoms due to their increased emotional control. The fact that EI training can be included in PMS management programs underscores the potential benefit of including EI training in PMS management programs. Future research efforts should focus on investigating how EI can influence PMS symptoms and the effectiveness of EI interventions in managing PMS symptoms.

3.3.1 IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Women suffering from PMS should be encouraged by healthcare providers to incorporate emotional intelligence training into their treatment plans to ease their symptoms.
- In addition to psychological support services, educational programs aimed at improving emotional intelligence can be used to reduce the emotional, psychological, and physical implications of PMS, thereby improving a woman's overall health.

3.3.2 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- There was only a study of women aged 20-45 in Hyderabad, and it would have been more accurate if more females from different regions had been included in the study in order to draw more accurate conclusions.
- In this study, the sample size ($n = 50$) limits the generalizability of the findings due to the small sample size. There is a need for future research that will utilize larger samples and longitudinal designs in order to confirm these findings and to understand the underlying mechanisms.

3.3.3 FUTURE SUGGESTIONS

- The Premenstrual Syndrome will have a severe impact on a woman's mental health and, therefore, it will be possible to investigate their psychological well-being and quality of life in the future.
- The study could have been replicated with a larger sample size and a more representative population since it only conducted the study in Hyderabad at this time.

REFERENCES

- Biggs, W. S., & Demuth, R. H. (2011). Premenstrual syndrome and premenstrual dysphoric disorder. *American Family Physician*, 84(8), 918-924.
- Brackett, M. A., & Salovey, P. (2006). Measuring emotional intelligence with the Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test (MSCEIT). *Psicothema*, 18(1), 34-41.
- Cunningham, J., Yonkers, K. A., O'Brien, S., & Eriksson, E. (2009). Update on research and treatment of premenstrual dysphoric disorder. *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 17(2), 120-137.
- Freeman, E. W. (2003). Premenstrual syndrome and premenstrual dysphoric disorder: Definitions and diagnosis. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 28, 25-37.
- Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. Bantam Books.
- Lustyk, M. K. B., Widman, L., Paschane, A. A., & Ecker, E. (2004). Stress, quality of life and physical activity in women with varying degrees of premenstrual symptomatology. *Women & Health*, 39(3), 35-44.
- Rapkin, A. J., & Winer, S. A. (2009). Premenstrual syndrome and premenstrual dysphoric disorder: Quality of life and burden of illness. *Expert Review of Pharmacoeconomics & Outcomes Research*, 9(2), 157-170.
- Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., Hall, L. E., Haggerty, D. J., Cooper, J. T., Golden, C. J., & Dornheim, L. (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 25(2), 167-177.
- Petrides, K. V., Pérez-González, J. C., & Furnham, A. (2004). On the criterion and incremental validity of trait emotional intelligence. *Cognition and Emotion*, 18(5), 562-578.
- Yonkers, K. A., O'Brien, P. M. S., & Eriksson, E. (2008). Premenstrual syndrome. *The Lancet*, 371(9619), 1200-1210.